

Admissibility of DNA Evidence in Bangladesh: Options and Challenges

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Abstract

This article explores the scope for the use of DNA typing as evidence in the proceeding of courts in Bangladesh. DNA is the fundamental building block for the entire genetic makeup of human being that comes into the aids of courts to unfold complex issues of civil and criminal nature. Like some other countries, Bangladesh has enacted DNA Act providing for the admissibility of DNA evidence in civil and criminal proceedings. Judges and lawyers, however, have often to face challenges in overcoming objections to the admissibility of DNA evidence. In addition, checking misuse of DNA profiling is a serious issue that should be handled strictly. This paper makes a critical analysis of the existing legal scholarships, relevant legislation, and case laws to pinpoint the challenges in regard to the use of DNA evidence in Bangladesh. The author argues that absence of a legal protocol in regard to the standard of admissibility of DNA evidence, inadequate laboratory standards and techniques, lack of training of judges and lawyers, and investigation officers on forensic science create obstacles to use of DNA evidence.

Keywords: DNA Profile, Crime Scene, Authenticity, Accuracy, Admissibility.

1. Introduction

DNA is called the fingerprint of 21st century that can conclusively identify a person and thereby can either link a suspect to, or eliminate him from, a crime. As per *Edmond Locard's* Exchange Principle that every contact leaves a trace, DNA is one of the important evidence the investigating officers collect from crime scenes that can lead to a significant breakthrough in criminal investigation. However, DNA technology has given rise to legal and technical

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challenges in legal proceedings in Bangladesh, with respect to the proof of any crime of dispute. Unlike in some other countries, the people involved in the administration of justice such as lawyers, investigating officers and judges in Bangladesh are hardly skilled enough to properly evaluate the DNA evidence. An underlying cause for this scenario may be attributed to the shortcomings in the existing legal system and the absence of a functioning infrastructural mechanism as well as the lack of a skilled staff. Considering the huge number of cases pending before the courts and the remarkably poor conviction rate,² it is imperative to exploit the benefit of DNA technology both in civil and criminal proceedings. Effective use of DNA evidence would have undoubtedly improved the quality of justice or prevented miscarriage of justice. This paper seeks to contribute to the law of evidence by way of ascertaining the barriers to the admissibility of DNA evidence.

2.1 Conceptualizing DNA Evidence

Deoxyribonucleic Acid (DNA) is the chemical dispatcher for genetic information,³ while DNA evidence is biological material from which DNA is or can be extracted.⁴ DNA contains the hereditary materials that are used in the development and functioning of all known living organisms.⁵ The reason it is called ‘deoxyribonucleic acid’ is that it is an acid that is found in every cell of the human body which contains lots of sugar group (ribo) attached to it and each sugar group has a missing oxygen molecule (deoxy)⁶ that encodes and carries the entire hereditary information of each individual.

The important feature of DNA for forensic purposes is that with the exception of identical twins, no two individuals have the same DNA configuration.⁷ The DNA tests allow forensic scientists to look at DNA molecules from an individual or a piece of evidence implicated/concerned and

² The rate of conviction in Bangladesh is below 15%; *vide*, the Workshop Paper of ADB on ‘*Strengthening the Criminal Justice System*’ ADB Regional Workshop in Dhaka, held on 30–31 May 2006, available at <https://think-asia.org/bitstream/handle/11540/2949/strengthening-criminal-justice-system.pdf?sequence=1>, retrieved on May 13, 2018.

³ Michael J. Pelczar, Jr. et al., *Microbiology: Concepts and Applications* 350-400 (1993) (explaining the structure and characteristics of (DNA); Lansing M. Prescott et al., *Microbiology* 193-201, 236-307 (2d ed. 1993)

⁴ *ABA Standards for Criminal Justice: DNA Evidence*, (3d ed.) the American Bar Association, USA, 2007.

⁵ Walter Hoffmann, *If Evolution is the Answer Then What’s the Question?* Xlibris Corporation, 2011.

⁶ Spencer Wells, *Deep Ancestry: Inside the Genographic Project: the Landmark DNA Quest to Decipher our Distant Past*, National Geographic Society, 2006.

⁷ Ann Barbara Hocking et al, ‘DNA, Human Rights and The Criminal Justice System’ *eLaw Journal: Australian Journal of Human Rights*, Vol.3, 1997 <<http://www.austlii.edu.au/au/journals/AJHR/1997/index.html>> retrieved on 12 June 2017>

compare them with DNA samples from other sources.⁸ The DNA evidence can establish, to a virtual certainty, the presence or the absence of a defendant at the scene of the crime⁹ and thereby come into the aid of the court to link or eliminate a person to or from a crime.

The DNA evidence first made its way into the courts in 1986, when police in England asked molecular biologist Alec Jeffrey, who had begun investigating the use of DNA for forensics, to use DNA to verify the confession of a 17-year-old boy in two rape-murders in the English Midlands. The tests proved that the teenager was in fact not the perpetrator. Instead, the actual offender was eventually caught using the DNA testing.¹⁰ The first DNA-based conviction in the United States took place in 1987 when the Circuit Court in the Orange County, Florida, convicted Tommy Lee Andrews for rape after DNA tests matched his DNA from a blood sample with that of semen traces found in the victim's body or costume.¹¹ In the constitutional case of *Bangladesh Jatiyo Mahila Ainjibi Samity (BJMAS) vs. Ministry of Home Affairs and Others*,¹² a former Deputy Inspector General of Police was held accused of illegally having the custody of more than seven children, on the basis of the DNA evidence. The brief facts of the case is that after reading the news item of seven children's delivery of the wife of a former Deputy Inspector General of Police (DIG) in a single instance of pregnancy, a serious doubt was created about their parenthood in the mind of the general public. Suspicion was also created amongst the people as to the paternity of the seven children that prompted different organization to move the Court with a writ petition for an order of DNA test of the 7 children. In a civil revision case¹³ on dower and maintenance for the petitioner and her child, the issue of legitimacy of the child Md. Biman came up. The plaintiff Beautiful Bibi filed an application for DNA (deoxyribonucleic acid) test of the child Md. Biman and also of the defendant Saydur Rahman and for recording

⁸ U.S. Congress Office of Technology Assessment, *Genetic Witness: Forensic Uses of DNA Tests*, at 3-6, 41-50; Prescott et al., *Ibid*.

⁹ George Bundy Smith and Janet A. Gordon, *the Admission of DNA Evidence in State and Federal Courts*, 65 *Fordham L. Rev.* 2465 (1997). Available at < <http://ir.lawnet.fordham.edu/flr/vol65/iss6/4>>

¹⁰ Lisa Calandro, Dennis J. Reeder and Karen Cormier, "Evolution of DNA Evidence for Crime Solving - A Judicial and Legislative History" *Forensic Magazine*, 2005, available at <<http://www.forensicmag.com/article/2005/01/evolution-dna-evidence-crime-solving-judicial-and-legislative-history>, retrieved on January 18, 2017>

¹¹ *Andrews v. State*, 533 So. 2d 841 (Fla. Dist. Ct. App. 1988)

¹² Writ Petition No. 5359 of 2006, available at

<http://www.supremecourt.gov.bd/resources/documents/216639_Writ_Petition_5359-06.pdf, retrieved on January 18, 2017>

¹³ *Beautiful Bibi vs. Sydur Rahman*, 67 DLR (2015), P.1.

additional evidence on the matter. The High Court Division of the Supreme Court of Bangladesh held that the DNA test report prepared by the Government DNA Laboratory was a credible piece of evidence. It was also held that DNA evidence is accepted worldwide as a reliable scientific method for various purposes including determination of parentage.

2.2 Collection of DNA Evidence

Collection and preservation of DNA evidence is a great challenge for the prosecution inasmuch as the admissibility of the DNA evidence before the court always depends on its accurate and proper collection, preservation and documentation which can satisfy the court that the evidence put in front of it is reliable.¹⁴ In order to submit a piece of DNA evidence for the admission thereof by the court, the prosecution has to produce to courts the particulars of every stage of collecting the evidence, the testing procedure followed and result found in laboratories, and an interpretation of the DNA evidence. DNA evidence may be collected from the body of persons, dead bodies, from crime scenes or from other locations. However, a complete guideline on the use of the DNA has yet to be emerged. Implementation of the guideline for collecting DNA evidence as provided by the Deoxyribonucleic Acid (DNA) Act has become problematic for the absence of implementing Rules.¹⁵

Collection of DNA samples from body of victims, accused and others

Adequate caution must be taken in collecting DNA samples from people in order to ensure their privacy, dignity, and human rights, as it is an established principle that individuals own their own DNA and no one can use it without authorization.¹⁶ According to International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR), no one shall be subjected to medical and scientific experimentation without their free consent.¹⁷ As a ratifying country to ICCPR, Bangladesh has included the above provision in the Deoxyribonucleic Acid (DNA) Act. Accordingly, without

¹⁴ Nirpat Patel, *et al.* “The Role of DNA in Criminal Investigation – Admissibility in Indian Legal System and Future Perspectives” *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Invention*, Volume 2, Issue 7, 2013, PP.15-21.

¹⁵ Deoxyribonucleic Acid (DNA) Act, Section 39.

¹⁶ Annas, ‘Genetic Privacy’, in David Lazer (ed), *DNA and the Criminal Justice System: The Technology of Justice*, MIT Press, 2004.

¹⁷ International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR), Art.7

written consent of the concerned person or the order of the competent court, as the case may be, and without the presence of at least two witnesses, DNA samples cannot be collected.¹⁸

As per section 4, the Police officer will request any victim, suspect or accused or any person involved in the alleged crime for providing a DNA sample and in no circumstances the police can compel the individual so to provide a DNA sample.¹⁹ In case the person so requested for a DNA sample fails to give consent within three hours, he/she will be deemed to have refused to give consent and the fact of such refusal shall be written in a prescribed form to be submitted to a competent court praying for an order of collecting DNA sample.²⁰ The court after hearing both the parties and considering the documents before it may order for the collection of DNA sample.²¹ Once the above formalities are complied with, DNA samples are collected and then sent forward to the forensic laboratory.²² In rape cases, for instance, the forensic exhibits like cloth worn by the victims, undergarments, bed-sheets, etc, internal vaginal swabs, and slides of microscopic examination, along with the blood samples of the victim and/or the accused person, are collected. The vaginal swabs should be collected within 72 hours of the alleged incidence. If the medical examination is delayed more than 72 hours, the above forensic exhibits must be sent to the laboratory along with the victim/victim's blood sample.

In order to collect DNA samples from a suspect with a murder, the National Forensic DNA Profiling Laboratory (NFDPL) requires the production of forensic exhibits that might have been left by the suspects, such as weapon, garments, hat, eyeglasses chewing gum, cigarette butts, tooth picks etc. along with the tissue sample from the victim and blood samples from the suspects. For the identification of the deceased, the blood samples of the nearest relations like mother, father, husband, wife and children along with the biological sample or objects relevant to the case (body parts, body remains such as bones, teeth and hairs with root, used cloths etc.) are required. The exhibit(s) should be packed and sealed in a paper bag without using polythene or

¹⁸ *Vide*, the Deoxyribonucleic Acid (DNA) Act, 2014, Ss. 4,6,10.

¹⁹ *Ibid*, section 6(1).

²⁰ *Ibid*, section 7.

²¹ *Ibid*, section 8.

²² Procedures for Collection, Preservation and Transportation of Sample for DNA Analysis, available at <<http://www.mspvaw.gov.bd/images/DownloadedFile/scp.pdf>, retrieved on 2 July 2017>

plastic bags. All the samples should accompany a Forwarding Note (Form 1),²³ a Sexual Assault Examination Form for the victim (Form 3),²⁴ and an Identification Form (Form 2)²⁵ for the accused, duly filled in and signed in the presence of a witness (Magistrate/Public Representative/Medical Officer).

Collection of DNA samples from the crime scene

‘Crime scene’ is a place where a crime has been committed or where an object is found from the victim’s body or from the body of any suspected person or an object carried in there by any relevant person, or where an object related to the crime is found.²⁶ Crime scene investigation (CSI) is one of the significant segments of criminal investigation. Of the various kinds of evidence encountered in the crime scene, the most useful evidence is DNA evidence. In order to exploit the DNA evidence, the investigating officer (IO) needs to know where to look for it, how to collect it, and how to package it.²⁷ The most common things usually looked for as a DNA evidence at the crime scene are blood, semen, hair, and saliva. DNA may also be found in urine, skin cells, perspiration, teeth, bone, and internal organs of a human body. If a bullet goes clean through the suspect, the bullet itself can be tested for traces of DNA. After all, DNA can be traced on anything relevant, from dirty laundry to eyeglasses, cigarettes, bottles, and drinking glasses, partial fingernails (both broken and clipped), masks, gloves, the steering wheel of a car, door knobs and handles, and cabinets. All these items should be collected and tested for the purpose of determining DNA.

While collecting DNA from crime scene, it is imperative to identify the victim’s DNA as well as the DNA of the suspects and anyone else who had access to the evidence and to guard against contamination.²⁸ Contamination is a serious issue to use DNA evidence into the admissibility of

²³Prescribed by the National Forensic DNA Profiling Laboratory (NFDPL)
<<http://www.mspvaw.gov.bd/images/DownloadedFile/scp.pdf>, retrieved on 2 July 2017>

²⁴ Ibid

²⁵ Ibid

²⁶ The Deoxyribonucleic Acid (DNA) Act, 2014, S. 2(1)

²⁷ Dick Warrington, *DNA Collection and Packaging*, Forensic Science Magazine

<<https://www.forensicmag.com/article/2009/04/dna-collection-and-packaging>, retrieved on 4 July 2017>

²⁸ Ibid

the court. In order to avoid contamination, the persons involved should follow the following procedures as prescribed by the National Forensic DNA Profiling Laboratory (NFDPL):²⁹

- i. to wear gloves while handling an evidence;
- ii. to handle on item at a time and change the gloves before starting another one;
- iii. to avoid touching the area where DNA might exist;
- iv. to avoid talking, sneezing, and coughing over the evidence;
- v. to avoid eating, drinking or smoking when collecting the evidence; and
- vi. to avoid touching nose, face and mouth when collecting evidence.

After collecting DNA evidence from the crime scene, caution should be taken in packaging and transporting the same to the laboratory. The DNA evidence should be air-dried before packing into new paper bags or envelopes which will have to be properly labeled and sealed and signed by the investigating officer in presence of a witness, e.g. Magistrate or Public Representative or Medical Officer. Then the DNA evidence is to be sent to the laboratory through the chain of custody with proper documentation.³⁰ The investigating officer will have to ensure complete documentation as well as the legality, relevance, authenticity, integrity and continuity of the chain of possession of the DNA evidence.³¹

3. Admissibility of DNA Evidence in Courts

Admissibility and relevance is not the same thing. By relevance is meant the degree of connection and probative value between a fact that is given in evidence and the issue to be proved. Admissibility means the process whereby the court determines whether the law of evidence permits that relevant evidence to be received by the court. Evidential relevance is a question of fact which is a duty of lawyers to prove, meaning that the counsels need to decide whether to tender such evidence in the court for the purpose of admissibility. On the other hand, admissibility refers to the quality of something for being admitted by the court as any evidence.³²

²⁹ Procedures for Collection, Preservation and Transportation of Sample for DNA Analysis, available at <<http://www.mspvaw.gov.bd/images/DownloadedFile/scp.pdf>> retrieved on 2 July 2017.

³⁰ Ibid.

³¹ BR Sharma, *Scientific Crime Investigation*, New Delhi, Universal Law Publishing Co. Pvt. Ltd., 2006, p. 158

³² *Public Prosecutor vs. Dato Seri Anwar Bin Ibrahim*, Federal Court of Malaysia (Appellate Jurisdiction) Criminal Appeal No: 05-21-02/2014, available at <<http://elawjournal.com/wp-content/uploads/cases/2017/11/3-cedbc82cf352ac05add0c8f775c23216/05-21-02-2014.pdf>> retrieved on 18 April 2018.

Once the evidence in question passes the test of relevance, it is most likely to be taken as admissible evidence.

It is a well known maxim in the Evidence Act that ‘all admissible facts are relevant, but all relevant facts are not admissible.’ When the court admits the evidence with regard to a fact, it is presumed that the court has first been satisfied that the fact is relevant for the purpose of proving the fact in issue.³³ But once a fact is proved to be relevant, there cannot be any presumption that the fact would be admitted by the court as there may be bars in law to its admission into evidence. For instance, ‘privileged communications’ may be shown to be relevant, yet the court may not admit them generally in evidence.³⁴

Section 45 of the Evidence Act,³⁵ provides that when the Court has to form an opinion upon a point of science, or art, or as to identity of hand writing or finger impressions, the opinions upon that point of persons specially skilled in science or art, or in questions as to identity of handwriting or finger impressions are relevant facts. As such forensic evidence, which includes DNA evidence, is relevant fact.

Again, the DNA Act³⁶ categorically provides that a report containing DNA profile may be treated as admissible evidence. But still there is a vacuum in law as to what would be the standard of admissibility. The major challenge for the legal actors to determine the validity and reliability of the DNA evidence is to establish the fact that the same bears the authenticity and accuracy in terms of scientific standards. The common flaws in this regard that may affect the validity and reliability of DNA forensic evidence include, *inter alia*, the inadequate laboratory standards and techniques such as insufficient DNA sample size, deterioration and contamination of the DNA sample, improper test procedures, false positive identification, and false negative results.

To regard a DNA sample as admissible being within the domain of judicial discretion, the court may adopt the internationally accepted standard for determining the admissibility of DNA Evidence. In general, two standards are used globally to determine the admissibility of DNA

³³ Muhammad Nazrul Islam, *Reflections on the Law of Evidence*, Dhaka, M.N. Islam, 1995, p. 486.

³⁴ Sections 121-131, the Evidence Act (Act No. 1 of 1872).

³⁵ Section 45, *Ibid*.

³⁶ Section 37 of the Deoxyribonucleic Acid (DNA) Act, 2014 (Act No. X of 2014).

evidence, such as the “Frye standard” and the “Daubert standard.” The Frye standard originates from a 1923 case, *Frye v. United States*, where the US Supreme Court ruled that, to be admissible, DNA evidence must be “sufficiently established to have gained general acceptance in the particular field in which it belongs.”³⁷ The Daubert standard is derived from the 1993 case *Daubert v. Merrell Dow Pharmaceuticals*, where the US Supreme Court went beyond the Frye standard to require that evidence must have sufficient scientific validity and reliability to be admitted as relevant “scientific knowledge” that would “assist the Trier of fact.”³⁸

In the United States, two major standards exist for deciding whether scientific findings will be admitted into evidence, i.e. the ‘general-acceptance’ test and the ‘sound-methodology’ standard. In addition, some jurisdictions have adopted special statutes that provide for the admissibility of genetic testing in general or of DNA analyses in particular in criminal or civil cases.³⁹ But in Bangladesh, neither the Deoxyribonucleic Acid (DNA) Act nor the Evidence Act sets forth any standard that should be met for the admissibility of the result of DNA analysis.

4. Options of Using DNA Evidence in Bangladesh

There are several options of using DNA evidence both in civil and criminal matters particularly in determining genetic relationship or the identification of paternity/maternity or of dead bodies, resolving issues concerning the legitimacy of children, resolving dispute regarding testamentary disposition, and investigation and prosecution of the grave offences like rape, culpable homicide, burglary and so forth.

4.1 Determining Genetic Relationship

Each person has a unique set of deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) sequencing (contained in body cells) that dictates an individual's physical characteristics and identity and stores hereditary information that passes from one generation to the next.⁴⁰ In *Bangladesh Jatiyo Mahila Ainjibi Samity vs. Ministry of Home Affairs and Others*, where the respondent, former Deputy Inspector

³⁷ *Frye v. United States*, 293 F. 1013 (D.C. Cir. 1923)

³⁸ *Daubert v. Merrell Dow Pharmaceuticals*, 113 2786 (S.Ct. 1993)

³⁹ National Research Council (US) Committee on DNA Forensic Science, *the Evaluation of Forensic DNA Evidence*, National Academy Press, Washington (DC), 1996 available at https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK232610/pdf/Bookshelf_NBK232610.pdf, retrieved on May 10, 2018.

⁴⁰ Natalie A. Bennett, A Privacy Review of DNA Databases, *Journal of Law and Policy*, Vol. 4, No. 3, (2008) p. 821, available at < https://kb.osu.edu/dspace/bitstream/handle/1811/72812/1/ISJLP_V4N3_821.pdf> retrieved on 12 April 2018.

General of Police, Anisur Rahman claimed that his wife gave birth to seven children at one pregnancy, it was held that by examining DNA molecule that contains all of our genetic information and its genetic code, the differences among individual can be scientifically and accurately determined.⁴¹ In this case, it was argued by the petitioners that the dispute as to the legal custody of the septuplet could not be resolved unless there was a DNA test of them and their alleged parents. Taking into consideration of the above argument, the High Court Division (HCD) of the Supreme Court of Bangladesh directed for two types of DNA tests in that case: ‘Sibling DNA Test’ of seven children to ascertain whether or not they are septuplet (whether each of seven children born at one birth) and ‘DNA Paternity Test’ to see whether they are the biological offspring of the alleged parents (respondents, i.e. former DIG Anisur Rahman and his wife).⁴² Result of Sibling DNA Test showed that all the seven children were unlikely to be related to each other. Based on the DNA test reports, the HCD ruled that the former DIG and his wife were not the biological parents of these seven children and nor were these children the septuplets. In *Frye v. United States*, it was held that DNA contained the code of a person’s hereditary propensities, parentage, and racial origins and more genetic information of biological relatives.⁴³ So DNA evidence can certainly assist the court to come up with a conclusive decision on the cases concerning genetic relationship.

4.2 Ascertaining Legitimacy of Children

The question of ascertaining legitimacy of a child arises when the putative father denies that the child is not the offspring of the marriage or when there exists uncertainty as to the paternity. In these circumstances, it is in the interest of morals that one may need to determine that the children born of a valid marriage are not of illicit unions.⁴⁴ According to section 112 of the Evidence Act 1872, if a child is born during the continuance of a valid marriage between his mother and any man, or within two hundred and eighty days after its dissolution, the child shall be conclusively presumed to be legitimate unless it can be shown that the parties to the marriage had no access to each other at any time when the child could have been begotten.⁴⁵ This section

⁴¹ 61 DLR (HCD) (2009) 371.

⁴² Ibid.

⁴³ Supra Note 36.

⁴⁴ Joseph Cullen Ayer, Jr. Legitimacy and Marriage, *Harvard Law Review*, Vol. 16, No. 1 (1902), pp. 22-42.

⁴⁵ Section 112 of the Evidence Act, 1872.

talks about ‘conclusive proof as to the legitimacy of a child’ born during a valid marriage or within 280 days of dissolution of a marriage. Conclusive proof cannot usually be rebutted unless it is allowed by law. The disputing party can rebut the presumption as to the legitimacy showing the concrete evidence establishing the fact that there was ‘no access meaning physical relation’ between parties to the marriage when the child could have been begotten.

The fact of ‘access or non-access’ could be established either by oral or documentary evidence. Now the question arises as to whether DNA test could be conducted to prove or disprove the fact of access or non-access. Review of some judgments of the Supreme Court of Bangladesh and the Supreme Courts of India reveals that the courts in Bangladesh and India are largely reluctant to allow DNA test under section 112. According to *Beautiful Bibi vs. Md. Sydur Rahman*,⁴⁶ though the DNA Test is accepted worldwide as a reliable scientific method for various purposes including the determination of parentage, courts must be cautious about the probable result of a DNA test exposing a child to a socially deplorable condition as a bastard child. Section 112 can be invoked when the paternity is questioned.⁴⁷ Paternity may come into question in any of the three circumstances: during continuance of a conception, in case of abortion or still born baby and in case the child is born alive. In any of the circumstances, the courts in Bangladesh and India consider the best interest of the child before allowing DNA test.

Conservative attitude of the courts in directing DNA test is justified and rationale on the ground that the illegitimate child shall have to bear a very miserable life in our society. The Kerala High Court observed that the stigma of illegitimacy is very severe since we have not any of the protective legislations as in England to protect illegitimate children.⁴⁸ The observation of the Kerala High Court is relevant in the socio-economic scenario of Bangladesh. Nonetheless, there is no legal bar to allow DNA test under section 112. In the Criminal Misc. Case, *Md. Mostafa vs. Bedena Khatun and Another*,⁴⁹ the respondent-petitioner alleged that she was raped by the appellant-accused (her cousin brother) and became pregnant which she could not yet feel. Subsequently, she got married to one Shahidul who left her after three month of the marriage when all the symptoms of pregnancy were exposed. Later on, the respondent-petitioner gave

⁴⁶ 67 DLR (2015), P.1

⁴⁷ M. Monir, *Law of Evidence*, Allahabad, University Book Agency, 2004, p. 528.

⁴⁸ *Goutam Kundu vs State of West Bengal And Another*, AIR 2295, 1993 SCR (3) 917.

⁴⁹ LEX/BDHC/0168/2012.

birth to a child. Under this situation, the High Court Division of the Supreme Court of Bangladesh observed that it was very easy to ascertain the fatherhood of the child by DNA test. The observation of this judgment makes it clear that the decision of the courts in regard to allowing DNA test may fluctuate depending on the facts and circumstances.

4.3 Identification of Dead Bodies

A dead body may require to be identified in both civil and criminal proceedings and for other purposes. In a criminal case, ascertaining the identity of the victim's dead body is *sine qua none* since it is said that there lies the clue to the offence in the identity of the victim. In *State vs. Md. Foysal Bin Nayem*,⁵⁰ one of the issues was whether the blood-stained dagger as the police seized from the crime scene was used to kill the victim? DNA test was conducted to ascertain the identification of the victim and the blood-stained dagger. The DNA test result found matching with the blood of the victim which bonded the sequence of evidence in proving the allegation against the perpetrators in that case.

Sometimes, it becomes necessary to identify a dead body and to ascertain medical cause of death for the settlement of insurance claims as well as payment of compensation for death in work place. For instance, the extremely decomposed bodies of some victims of Tazrin Fashions and Rana Plaza incidences were identified by matching the DNA samples collected from the bodies with those of their relatives.⁵¹ On April 28, 2013, a writ petition was filed at the High Court Division seeking arrest of the owner of Tazreen Fashions Limited for his ignorance.⁵² On June 8, 2013, the High Court Division directed the authority concerned to carry out the DNA tests of the families of 37 missing victims' of Tazreen Fashion fire⁵³ so that the bereaved families could be compensated.

⁵⁰ LEX/BDHC/0010/2017.

⁵¹ In 2013, Rana Plaza, a multi-storey building crushed down in Savar on the outskirts of the capital killing at least 1,134 people, mostly garment workers, and injuring several hundred others. More than 321 dead bodies were decomposed beyond recognition. Most of the decomposed bodies were identified through matching of their DNA with that of their family relatives.

⁵² S. M. Solaiman, Unprecedented Factory Fire of Tazreen Fashions in Bangladesh: Revisiting Bangladeshi Labor Laws in Light of Their Equivalents in Australia, *Hofstra Labor & Employment Law Journal*, Vol. 31, Issue 1, 2013, Article 3. Available at <http://scholarlycommons.law.hofstra.edu/hlelj/vol31/iss1/3>, retrieved on June 22, 2018.

⁵³ Fire broke out on 24 November 2012, in the Tazreen Fashion factory in the Ashulia district on the outskirts of Dhaka, leaving 117 people dead in the fire, and over 200 injured. 37 dead bodies were burned beyond recognition.

4.4 Investigation of Rape Cases

In a rape case, DNA test provides the courts a means of identifying the perpetrators with a high degree of certainty and confidence. By using DNA technology, the courts are in a better position to reach at a conclusion whereby convicting the real culprits.⁵⁴ DNA evidence is collected from the stains of blood or sperm on the clothes of the victim or accused or from blood/semen in vagina of the victim. The report of DNA test is the most significant medical evidence in a rape case⁵⁵ which is usually used to establish paternity of any issue born of rape, to examine fibres and pubic hairs and to identify the accused by matching his DNA blueprint and establishing his capacity to commit rape.

In a Writ Petition, *Naripokkho and others vs. Bangladesh and others*,⁵⁶ where the petitioners challenged the delay in recording a case following the gang rape of a Garo woman in a microbus in the capital, the High Court Division (HCD) directed that DNA tests must be conducted in all rape or sexual assault cases, and the DNA and other samples should be sent to lab within 48 hours of the occurrence.

In the murder of Sohagi Jahan Tonu, a 19-year-old student of Comilla Victoria Government College who was allegedly raped and murdered by unidentified miscreants, the first autopsy found no evidence of rape or murder.⁵⁷ The report created controversy and was subject to pungent criticism from different quarters. The High Court Division of the Supreme Court of Bangladesh ordered a second autopsy. The Second autopsy conducted in Comilla Medical College Hospital also failed to unveil the cause of death and therefore, was kept pending. Prior to the second autopsy, the crime lab of Criminal Investigation Department (CID) collected DNA from semen in Tonu's underwear. By analyzing the DNA, the CID found evidence of rape.⁵⁸ On the basis of the DNA test report, the medical board of Comilla Medical College finalized the second autopsy where it was concluded that Tanu was raped before being killed.⁵⁹

⁵⁴ *Syed Talib Hussain vs. the State*, LEX/FSPK/0005/2013.

⁵⁵ Medico-legal Evidence Collection Form of Rape Victim, Clause 17(d).

⁵⁶ Writ Petition No. 5541/2015.

⁵⁷ *Seven months into Tonu murder: Family losing hope of getting justice*. Dhaka Tribune, October 24, 2016.

⁵⁸ *Tonu murder: DNA test finds evidence of rape*, The Daily Star. May 16, 2016.

⁵⁹ *Tonu's 2nd autopsy finds evidence of 'sexual assault*, The Daily Star. June 12, 2016.

5. Challenges in Using DNA Evidence

In *Bangladesh Bar Council vs. A.K.M. Fazlul Kamir*,⁶⁰ the Appellate Division of the Supreme Court of Bangladesh held that this digital age has posed us with entirely a new phenomenon of legal challenges including the forensic evidence which has already revolutionized the law and legal practices. Though the Appellate Division made the casual comment in regard to the overall quality of legal education in Bangladesh, it is very much pertinent to actors of justice system who are involved in using DNA evidence as the above discussion reveals, the application of DNA testing for the case investigation process has opened a new opportunity for identifying criminals in Bangladesh. The challenges the actors have to face in using DNA evidence in administration of justice are many folds.

DNA technology has posed serious challenges to some legal and functional rights of an individual such as the right to privacy, right against self-incrimination.⁶¹ These rights of the individuals can be maintained by showing the greatest respect and precaution toward human rights and privacy issues as the Deoxyribonucleic Acid (DNA) Act provides for.

Sufficient number of forensic DNA labs with all modern amenities has not been established in Bangladesh. Law enforcing agencies send DNA samples to the National Forensic DNA Profiling Laboratory (NFDPL), the country's first ever forensic DNA laboratory. Established in 2005 at the Department of Forensic Medicine of Dhaka Medical College Hospital, it was given legal shape by the Deoxyribonucleic Acid (DNA) Act, 2014.⁶² Sophisticated Combined DNA Index System (CODIS) software was added to this laboratory in 2013.⁶³ The technology of DNA analysis and equipment used in this laboratory are claimed to be of international standard.⁶⁴ Yet there is a need for international accreditation and further professional training for the persons involved as scientists or technicians, in order to maintain quality.⁶⁵ The country's only DNA lab

⁶⁰25 BLT (2017) (AD) 158; 14 ADC (2017) 271; Manupatra LEX/BDAD/0004/2017

⁶¹ A. Z. M. Arman Habib, 'Deoxyribonucleic Acid (DNA) Act, 2014: A New Era in Criminal Justice System of Bangladesh' *Bangladesh Law Digest*, January 7, 2016, available at <<http://bdlawdigest.org/deoxyribonucleic-acid-dna-act-2014-a-new-era-in-criminal-justice-system-of-bangladesh.html>>

⁶²Section 14(3) of the DNA Act provides, "National Forensic DNA Profiling Laboratory located in Dhaka shall be deemed to have been established by the Government under this Act".

⁶³ On September 25, 2013, the FBI donated this software to promptly identify 321 unidentified dead bodies of Savar's Rana Plaza Tragedy.

⁶⁴ Sheikh Hafizur Rahman Karzon, "Interrelationship of Genetics and Criminal Behaviour: Challenges for Judges and Lawyers" *Dhaka University Law Journal, Studies Part-F*, Vol. 18, No. 1, (2007) 21.

⁶⁵ Review of Lessons Learned 2004 – 2010 Multi-Sectoral Programme on Violence against

is suffering from a number of constraints. One of the biggest constraints is the flawed manner in which DNA sample particularly evidence of rape is gathered and preserved. The screening lab and archive room of the laboratory are over-burdened with large number of DNA samples.⁶⁶

As per section 24 of the DNA Act, the government is required to establish a National DNA database with crime scene index, convict criminals' index and unknown person's index. Database of this kind could have been used in identifying the perpetrators who repeatedly involve in crimes. But no initiative has yet to be undertaken to establish such database. Consequently, it becomes difficult to maintain the record of DNA profiles prepared in lab by analyzing DNA samples collected from various sources.

The admissibility of DNA evidence is challenged by lawyers on two common grounds: authenticity and accuracy. The term 'authenticity' refers to the originality, showing the chain of custody from the source to court room via laboratory. The term 'accuracy' which is also known as 'sound- methodology' means the absence of mistakes or errors in the procedure followed in collection and analysis of DNA samples. Though the DNA evidence has been made admissible in the proceeding of courts,⁶⁷ judges and lawyers often face challenges in assessing the authenticity and accuracy of such evidence. Absence of guideline in law⁶⁸ setting forth the standard of admissibility of forensic evidence generally and DNA evidence particularly, and lack of training of judges and lawyers on forensic science are mainly responsible for such challenges.

Most judges and the lawyers do not have sufficient training and knowledge to peruse or use the DNA test reports. As a result, they blindly rely on the reports to form decisions as regard to the issue before the court. Such uncritical or uninformed reliance on DNA reports by courts/lawyers is evident from the analysis of the cases cited above. This will give rise to the chances of misusing DNA evidence.

Even in developed countries which are using hi-tech appliances in collecting and testing DNA samples, dozens of cases of DNA typing are reported to have been gone terribly wrong.⁶⁹ For

Women, Ministry of Women and Children Affairs.

⁶⁶ Prothom-alo, April 4, 2014.

⁶⁷ Section 37 of the Deoxyribonucleic Acid (DNA) Act, 2014 (Act No. X of 2014).

⁶⁸Section 39 of the Deoxyribonucleic Acid (DNA) Act, 2014 (Act No. X of 2014) mandated the government to promulgate the implementing Rules to accomplish the objectives of the Act, but the Rules is yet to be promulgated.

⁶⁹ Erin E. Murphy, *Inside the Cell: The Dark Side of Forensic DNA*, New York, Nation Books, 2015.

instance, in 1998, a woman was abducted at gunpoint in California, raped by two men, and dumped into a nearby field. Five days after the attack, she identified one Josiah Sutton and his friend as her possible attackers though they were not involved in the crime. Sutton was convicted of rape through DNA analysis and sentenced to 24 years imprisonment. After serving five years, Sutton was exonerated when it was established that the lab was completely wrong in their first report.⁷⁰ Hence, before deciding the admissibility of the result of DNA analysis, the judge must determine whether the applicable standard has been met so as to avoid technical and human error.

6. Concluding Remarks

After invention of DNA profiling in 1986 by Sir Alec Jeffrey, administration of justice was revolutionized particularly criminal investigation mechanism assumed a paradigm shift from the conventional mode of identification of suspects. While committing crimes, the perpetrators unknowingly leave some traces and DNA is one of them that result in important leads to identify the suspects comparing their DNA blueprints. However, this is a very challenging job to comply with due procedure in respect of collection and analysis of DNA samples as the aforementioned discussion reveals, any flaw in DNA analysis may inculcate an innocent person having no proximity with the crime. Law invests the courts with discretion to evaluate DNA profiling reports in order to determine admissibility of DNA evidence but did not set forth any standard for the admissibility of the same.

Most judges and the lawyers do not have sufficient training and knowledge to check the validity of the DNA test reports. As such, uncritical or uninformed reliance on DNA reports by courts/lawyers creates the chances of misusing DNA evidence. The investigation officers (IO) and some staff of forensic labs are often found not to be trained to ensure complete documentation of the DNA evidence. Moreover, flawed manner in collection and preservation of DNA samples and improper test procedures followed in labs leads to the deterioration and contamination of the DNA sample.

Therefore, it is recommended that judges, lawyers and investigation officials involved in administration of justice have the orientation as to the procedure of DNA analysis relevant to the

⁷⁰ Ibid.

administration of justice. To this end, legislative and institutional initiative should be adopted to form an efficient and strong investigation and judicial mechanism comprising the experts of different disciplines and providing it with modern equipments and necessary logistic supports. As per the requirement of Deoxyribonucleic Acid (DNA) Act, implementing Rules will have to be promulgated setting down the standards in regard to the documentation of DNA samples and the evaluation of the legality, relevance, authenticity, integrity, and continuity of the chain of possession of the DNA evidence.